

1 **A component of the B-cell receptor, CD79A/B expressed in metastasis to the brain in both**
2 **malignant melanoma and breast cancer undergoes differential epigenetic modification during**
3 **disease progression and metastasis.**

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8 We used published whole genome DNA methylation data to study methylation marks across the
9 melanoma tumor genome by whole genome methylation profiling, in primary tumors and melanoma brain
10 metastases, to understand if epigenetic modification of genomic regulatory and coding sequences (as
11 opposed to mutation, translocation, or gene expression changes resulting from trans-differentiation) was
12 responsible for these changes which appears to be requisite during solid tumor metastasis to the brain in
13 humans.

14 We found genomic sites at CD79a and CD79b that were among the most differentially methylated across
15 the human melanoma tumor genome when comparing primary tumor to brain metastasis, indicating that
16 selective pressure during metastasis to the brain drives changes in expression of lymphocyte components
17 including CD79a and CD79b through epigenetic mechanisms, changes whose biological relevance and
18 intent appear patterned or designed. Functional analysis supported a role for a CD79-centered or
19 CD79-driven gene expression program that guided an evolutionary path governed by interactions at the
20 cell surface between the circulating tumor cell and the lymph node, which then supported metastasis to
21 the CNS.
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We observed during study of central nervous system metastasis in human cancer, in solid tumors with tendency to spread to the CNS: breast cancer and lung cancer, recurrent differential expression of membrane receptor components of the T and B lymphocyte, including CD8a, T cell co-receptor components CD3d and CD3e, and co-receptor subunits for the B-cell receptor (BCR) CD79a and CD79b. Of seeming biological significance, each of these components was first activated during progression from primary tumor to lymph node metastasis, and then later silenced from progression from lymph node metastasis to CNS metastasis.

Remarkably, intracellular machinery specific to the B and T lymphocyte, including ITK and BTK, were also among the genes whose expression most obviously fluctuated in concert during disease progression from the primary tumor to the lymph node metastasis, and then from lymph node disease to brain metastasis. We have described differential expression of BCR components CD79a and CD79b in a third solid tumor with tendency to spread to the CNS, metastatic melanoma, but the molecular mechanism by which expression of hematopoietic cell-specific machinery is modulated during transformation and metastasis in human lung cancer, human breast cancer and humans melanoma that spreads to the brain remains unknown.

Changes in subunit composition in the cancer cell will be governed by mutation, translocation, gene expression changes resulting from trans-differentiation, or selection pressure-associated epigenetic modification. We studied here whole genome methylation in the malignant melanoma tumor genome.

Results

Figure 1: CD79A and CD79B are differentially methylated in the melanoma tumor genome.

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n=4 primary tumor (melanoma; stage II)

n=16 brain metastasis (melanoma; stage IV)

Whole genome methylation profiling

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DM
cg21816743	5.47e-04	-4.1467664	-0.146879	-3.48e-01	CD79B	14461/480840	
cg05921699	6.46e-03	3.0583164	-2.455083	2.66e-01	CD79A	50424/480840	

Figure 2: CCR7, FAM129C, and PTPRCAP, genes expressed in the lymph node, are CD79B co-regulated genes.

This data pointed to a principle which likely influenced CNS metastasis in solid organ malignancy; that genes co-regulated with CD79A/B that are enriched for expression in the lymph node will be differentially expressed during transformation, progression to lymph node metastasis, and metastasis to the CNS, a “similarity” principle highlighted by shared expression in genes at the metastatic site and genes differentially expressed in the tumor clone, which is likely a strong influence on the evolutionary path the primary tumor cell at the level of the lymph node metastasis, genes undergoing selection pressure in the tumor clone during homing, or even prior to this.

Figure 3: CD79B, a component of the B-cell receptor, is co-regulated with Siglec-10, which B-cells use to interact with the lymph nodes.

This data pointed to a second principle which likely influenced CNS metastasis in solid organ malignancy; that genes co-regulated with CD79A/B, genes of the B-cell receptor complex and genes of the B-cell, which physically interact with the lymph node, will be targets of selection pressure, quantitatively evident in differential expression when comparing the primary tumor, the non-transformed tissue from the tumor arose, the lymph node metastasis, and the CNS metastasis.

Discussion

We identified here differential methylation of CD79A and CD79B, components of the B-cell receptor in the melanoma tumor genome, and found that CD79B was co-regulated at the transcriptome level with genes expressed in the lymph node, like *CCR7* and *Fam129C* and genes expressed in the B-cell that mediate physical interactions with the lymph node, like *Siglec-10*.